

Marketing of Timber in Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

The term selling for money is vague, implying a very simple transfer of goods for money. There's better more comprehensive and methodical way— marketing timber. Marketing implies following proven chronological steps to arrive at a favourable results through advance planning, careful implementation, diligent oversight and responsible closure. Marketing generates more income while still addressing other important measures, such as establishment a new forest, protecting soil / water/wildlife resources, aesthetics and special places. Hence the present study on marketing of Timber in Thoothukudi District aims at evaluating how the timber, requirements of the customers in thoothukudi District are being matched by different timber suppliers in the district.

Introduction

Be it the peasant's hut of the kings, timber has been the principal material through the centuries for house building and furniture of the description. Timber is described as the term for wood, other than full wood, that is either sawn or prepared in some way; it is also used to denote a group of trees from which timber may be obtained or for food used in heavy construction, for example: ship building. The inherent features which keep timber in the forefront of raw materials are many and varied, but one of the chief attributes is its availability in many species, sizes, shapes and condition to suit almost every dement. It is naturally an aesthetically pleasing material because of the grain patterns and colour and its appearance may be easily enhanced by strains, lacquers and other finisher. It is easily shaped with tools, fastened with adhesives, nails, screws and bolts. However, there is one features of wood which is unique amongst all structural materials; it is crop which can be farmed whereas its competitors such as stone, metal, brick and plastics are all derived from exhaustible resources. This features is alone sufficient to ensure that wood will continue to be in use as a structural materials virtually forever and it is also likely to ensure that wood remains the cheaper of all structural materials. Through the ages, the unique characteristics and comparative abundance of wood have made it natural material

for homes and other structure, furniture, tools vehicles and decorative objects. Today, for the same reasons, wood is prized for a multitude of uses. Wood is as valuable as an engineering material as it ever in many cases technological advances have made it even more useful. The term marketing may mean things to many people. It may be the activity of buying or selling or specific market place such as a vegetable market. But marketing has actually evolved from its early origins in distribution and selling into a comprehensive philosophy for relating any organisation dynamically to its markets. Hence the present study deals with timber in Thoothukudi district.

Review of Literature

Morgan Snook (2016) in their article “Oregon Douglas Fir and sustainable Wood Choice in Solid Body Electric Guitars” conclude that this thesis explores alternative wood choice in solid body electric guitar manufacturing, with the focus being in long term resources sustainability, and how the choice of the wood affects the sound and manufacturing. Gibson Guitars is primary company of comparison because of its reliance of the tropical hardwood mahogany. Douglas fir is faster growing, and protected more heavily than mahogany, and can be acquired from the country in which the guitars are built. Douglas fir is comparable to mahogany in specific gravity, and the role of the guitar body in electric guitars has significantly less effect on the sound than in an acoustic instrument, and the final guitars sounds comparable to similar instrument made from other woods. The evidence is a fully functioning electric guitar with a body from Douglas fir.

Anna Kesikisaari (2017) in his article entitled, “The Impact of Recycled Raw Materials on the properties of Wood- plastic Composites” conclude that the results of the study showed that it is possible to use recycled raw materials as a part of wood- plastic composites. The lower price and some improved properties encourage using recycled materials, when the features of the composite are understood. Due to the tightening legalisation, there will be more material available for wood – plastic composites in the future. Reusing materials in wood- plastic composites will reduce the use of virgin materials.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To ascertain the different types of timber that are being marketed in Thoothukudi District.
2. To examine and evaluate the pricing objectives, policies and methods prevailing in the area under study.
3. To analyse and comprehend the various promotional techniques employed by the timber merchants in the study area.
4. To appraise and assimilate the alternative channels for marketing of timber in the area surveyed.
5. To identify and understand the profile of the timber traders in Thoothukudi District.
6. To summarise the findings and offer suitable suggestions, necessary for the successful marketing of timber in Thoothukudi District

Data and Methodology

The present study is both descriptive and empirical. This section describes briefly the research design employed in the study in terms of sources, collection of data and the statistical tools applied. The data required for the study have been collected from the both primary and secondary sources. Primary data have been collected through direct personal interviews from 60 timber traders in the study area, using a well – designed schedule which was finalized after careful testing through a pilot study. Secondary data were collected from published and unpublished sources. The former include encyclopaedia, standardized books, journal, magazines, periodicals and the report and

manuals of the government department having control directly or indirectly over timber marketing in Thoothukudi District.

Results and Discussion

Gender

Two way ANOVA is done in order to know whether the gender has any significant impact on the perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber. For the purpose, the respondent studied have been segregated into two categories (a) Female and (b) Male. The results of ANOVA is presented as follows

Table 1 ANOVA Output for Gender

Source of variation	Sun of square	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of square	Ratio of 'F'	Table Value
Between level of perception	613	2	306.5	1.007	19
Between gender	1944	1	1944	6.38	18.51
Residual	609	2	304.5		

Hypothesis

H_(01.) There is no significant different between two genders concerning the problems on perception.

It would be depicted from the Table 1 that, the obtained 'F' value 1.007 and 6.38 were less than the table values 19 and 18.51 respectively at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted and it could be concluded that, there is no significant relationship between gender and level of perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber.

Age - Group

Two way ANOVA is done in order to know whether the gender has any significant impact on the perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber. For the purpose, the respondents studied been segregated in to four categories (a)Upto 30years (b) 30-40 years,(c)40 -50 years and (d)50 years and above. The results of ANOVA are presented as follows.

Table 2 ANOVA output for Age group

Source of variation	Sun of square	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of square	Ratio of 'F'	Table Value
Between level of perception	306.5	2	153.25	30.77	5.14
Between age	215.37	3	71.79	14.42	4.76
Residual	29.87	6	4.98		

Hypothesis

H_(02.) There is no significant different between age group concerning the problems on perception.

It could be depicted from the Table2 that, the obtained 'F' value 30.77 and 14.42 were more than the table value 5.14 and 4.76 respectively at 5% level of significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected and it could be concluded that, there is significant relationship between age and level of perception towards opinion regarding the problems uncounted by while selling timber.

Educational Qualification

Two way ANOVA is done in order to know whether the educational qualification has any significant impact on the perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber. For the purpose, the respondents studied been segregated in to five categories (a) Up to Tenth standard (b) Hr. Secondary/ PUC,(c) Graduate,(d)Post graduate,(e) Professional. The results of ANOVA are presented as follows.

Table 3 ANOVA output for Educational Qualification

Source of variation	Sun of square	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of square	Ratio of 'F'	Table Value
Between level of perception	245.2	2	122.6	6.36	4.45
Between educational qualification	274.66	4	68.67	3.56	3.84
Residual	154.14	8	19.27		

Hypothesis

H_(O3.) There is no significant different between educational qualification concerning the problems on perception

It could be depicted from the Table that, the obtained 'F' values 6.36 were more than the table value 4.45, respectively at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypotheses were rejected and it could be concluded that, there is no significant relationship between educational qualification and level of perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber and 3.56 were less than the table value 3.84 respectively at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted and it could be concluded that, there is significant relationship between educational qualification and level of perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber.

Previous Occupation

Two way ANOVA is done in order to know whether the previous occupation has any significant impact on the perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by while selling timber. For the purpose, the respondents studied been segregated in to five categories (a)Agriculturist (b) Industrialist, (c) Trader,(d)Salaried employee and ,(e) Unemployed. The results of ANOVA are presented as follows.

Table 4 ANOVA Output for Previous Occupation

Source of variation	Sun of square	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of square	Ratio of 'F'	Table Value
Between level of perception	245.2	2	122.6	3.08	4.46
Between level previous occupation	140.1	4	35.025	1.14	3.84
Residual	318.7	8	39.84		

Hypothesis

H_{O4.} There is no significant different between previous occupation concerning the problems on perception

It could be depicted from the Table that, the obtained 'F' values 3.08 and 1.14 respectively at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted and it could be concluded that, there is no significance relationship between previous occupation and level of perception towards opinion regarding the problems encountered by the selling timber.

Consolidated Results of F – Test

The consolidated results of 'F' Test is given in Table

Consolidated Results of F – Test

S. No	Demographic factors	Level of perception				
		V1	V2	Calculated value	Table value	Difference in relationship
1	Gender	2	2	1.26	19.00	NS
		1	2	4.44	18.51	NS
2	Age	2	6	30.77	5.14	S
		3	6	14.42	4.76	S
3	Educational qualification	2	8	6.36	4.46	S
				3.56	3.84	NS
4	Previous occupational	2	8	3.08	4.46	NS
			8	1.14	3.84	NS

Conclusion

Timber, an aesthetically pleasing material gifted by nature, is widely used from time immemorial for a variety of purpose. It is a renewable and therefore in exhaustive in its suppliers. It has been closely associated with man's basic survival and development. The demand for timber has risen so sharply due to ever increasing population, rapid urbanization, growing transporting, improved packing needs, magnifying developmental and construction activities. This research on the whole, will be a highly successful one when the suggestions that are proposed are judiciously implemented. The timber merchants, the Government, the forest department and the customers should realise the importance of timber in our daily life and should therefore follow ethical ways to procure as well as sell it.

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